

ISic3476

I.Sicily inscription 3476

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, private collection (P. Cacia)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336070

1. Εύπρα[ξία] Ἡρακλεί-
2. δαι Ἡρακλείδα
3. ἐποίησε. vacat
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645097

EDCS 64500537

PHI 336070

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1276

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 41 no.15 fig.92

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